

H2AMI: Intuitive Human to Aerial Manipulator Interface

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Abstract—Aerial manipulators are unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) coupled with robotic manipulators (RMs). Their ability to interact with the environment and perform service and maintenance tasks in hard-to-reach places makes them interesting for a wide range of applications and industries. Human pose estimation relates to the problem of estimating human body pose. In this paper, we present an intuitive aerial manipulator human interface which enables the control of the aerial manipulator based on the operator’s movements. The operator’s motions are captured with an affordable depth camera and pose estimation is performed with a neural network. We have developed a system that enables intuitive decoupled control of the unmanned aerial vehicle and robotic manipulator. We compared two neural network architectures for the human pose estimation as a part of the H2AMI. System performance was verified in the simulation environment.

Index Terms—human pose estimation; robotic manipulation; robotic demonstration;

I. INTRODUCTION

The main driving forces of technological progress in recent years are robotics and artificial intelligence. Deep learning as a branch of artificial intelligence continues to solve a wide variety of tasks in the wild, which were considered impossible just a decade ago. Most interesting ones are related to visual perception, sound and speech recognition as well as text classification and recognition. All that progress has flooded the field with pretrained, open source neural network models which can be started and used in the matter of hours. Disruptive technology as deep learning as well as other fields of machine learning are becoming vital parts of almost any *autonomous* robot system that has to perform some task in the wild. Besides deep learning, price of robotic components, PCs and the democratization of software (open-source communities) led to a significant acceleration of robotics development. Nowadays we can witness humanoid robots doing human-like agile movements that were in the domain of science fiction just a decade ago. In addition to that, one can witness UAVs such as hobby drones used for amateur cinematography as well as monitoring and surveillance more than ever. Most interesting applications in the area of aerial manipulators (AMs) are ones that facilitate the full potential of a such system. AM for push-and-slide inspection in the industrial inspection as described in [1]. Apart from push-and-slide inspection, infrastructure contact inspection is presented in [2] with a fully actuated aerial manipulator. There are also specially designed aerial manipulators for the inspection of pipe arrays as shown in [3]. One of the examples of interesting and useful

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Fig. 1: Illustration of human to aerial manipulator interface (H2AMI). H2AMI enables the operator to use one hand to control the UAV position, and the other hand to control the robot manipulator configuration.

interactions with the environment includes valve turning by aerial manipulator as described in [4]. Aside from interaction with the environment, aerial manipulators can be used as co-operators with human workers for the purpose of the robot tool handover [5], [6] and aerial-devices delivery [7].

Most of aerial manipulators today are controlled in the same way as the classical UAVs, by using radio controller (RC) joystick. Such control is severely lacking especially taking into consideration the control of the aerial manipulator. In this paper, we present control of the aerial manipulator based on the human pose estimation. We believe that the development of intuitive control could be beneficial for further application of such technology. The contribution of this paper is twofold:

- 1) *Intuitive aerial manipulator control based on visual human pose estimation*
- 2) *Comparison of different human pose estimation algorithms for the purpose of the aerial manipulator control*

The paper is divided into seven sections. Section II contains a brief review of the state-of-the-art on human-machine interfaces for UAVs and robot manipulators. Section III presents the methodology used to develop intuitive aerial manipulator human interface. Section IV presents control of the UAV and the RM with H2AMI. Section V includes an explanation of the simulation experiments done to verify the developed interface. Section VI concludes the paper with findings and open questions, as well as possible further research directions. In Appendix VII, there is comparison of different human pose estimation algorithms for the task of aerial manipulator control.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section we present related work that couples robotic manipulation and deep learning pose estimation. Bohg *et al.* showed in [8] that it is possible to use depth camera and pixel-wise part classification of a robot arm for markerless pose estimation of the robotic manipulator. Authors state that the inspiration for determining robot arm pose from single depth image is based on human pose estimation and can be found in [9]. In [10] Lee *et al.* present a similar system for determining camera pose from single monocular image of the known robot. System employs neural network for robot pose estimation trained on synthetically generated data using domain randomization. Paper includes study of the system performance with three different cameras, where Intel Realsense D415 is best in comparison with XBOX360 Kinect and Azure Kinect. Bujalance *et al.* presented real-time gestural control of robotic arm based on human pose estimation in [11]. For the human pose estimation, OpenPose [12] is used. For 3D reconstruction, they aided pose estimation with Human Mesh Recovery [13]. Based on the 3D human pose they presented two different control methods. One method of control used Jacobian and velocity kinematics to servo end-effector tool on shorter distances, and another method used direct mapping between human joint angles and robot arm. Besides robot arm manipulator control, human pose estimation has been used to control UAVs. Marinov *et al.* [14] presented Pose2Drone, framework which uses human pose estimation as component in one of the software modules used to control UAV. UAV is controlled based on discrete operator body gestures, and predefined movements. For the human pose estimation, authors employed OpenPose due to face recognition capabilities. Palossi *et al.* [15] presented PULP-FrontNet, which is convolutional neural network for visual human pose estimation suitable for IoT devices e.g. nano-drones. It shows great potential, especially taken in consideration size and energy consumption of such drones, which could be of vital importance for the search-and-rescue tasks.

III. METHODOLOGY

To derive the proposed human-machine interface, we rely on existing human pose estimation technology, which is briefly described in this section. The first step in evaluating the proposed algorithm is to deploy it in a simulation environment. As part of the methodology used to evaluate the proposed framework we briefly describe the dynamic model used to simulate the aerial manipulator. For completeness, we provide all the parameters used in the simulation.

A. Aerial manipulator model

In this paper we employed a quadrotor coupled with an anthropomorphic robot manipulator presented in [16]. Aerial manipulator (AM) is simulated using Gazebo plugins for rotor dynamics presented in [17]. The dynamic model used for the control of the AM is decoupled as presented in [18], which implies that we control UAV and robot manipulator, independently. Parameters of the UAV dynamic model are

presented in table I. For the control of the UAV, cascaded PID controllers are used with parameters presented in table II. The output of the cascaded position control is input to the cascaded attitude control. Cascaded position control is comprised of P controllers (P_x, P_y, P_z) whose input is the difference (error) between desired and current UAV pose. The output of those controllers is the velocity setpoint. The difference between velocity setpoint and current measured linear velocity is velocity error which is fed to the PI (P_{xyz}, I_{xyz}) controllers. The output of the PI controllers are attitude setpoints (roll (ϕ), pitch (θ), yaw (ρ) angles). The difference between attitude setpoint and current attitude is used as angle input to the PID controllers ($P_{\theta,\delta,\phi}, I_{\theta,\delta,\phi}, D_{\theta,\delta,\phi}$) of the attitude cascade. The output of those controllers is the attitude rate setpoint. The attitude rate setpoint compared to the current attitude rate is fed to the last PID controllers ($P_{v\theta,\delta,\phi}, I_{v\theta,\delta,\phi}, D_{v\theta,\delta,\phi}$) of the attitude cascade, and output is changed in the motor speeds.

TABLE I: Parameters used for quadrotor modeling in the simulation.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
motor constant c_t	$8.54810^{-6} \text{ kgm/s}^2$	body mass	2.083 kg
UAV arm length a_l	0.314 m	rotor mass	0.01 kg
body inertia I_{xx}	0.08269 kgm^2	rotor radius	0.154 m
body inertia I_{yy}	0.08629 kgm^2		
body inertia I_{zz}	0.0104 kgm^2		

TABLE II: Controller parameters for the position control of the AM

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
P_x, P_y	2.0	P_z	10.0
P_{vx}, P_{vy}	0.5	I_z	0.5
I_{vx}, I_{vy}	0.1	P_{vz}	350.0
I_{vz}	40.0	P_ψ	1.0
P_ϕ, P_θ	0.5	I_ψ	0.001
I_ϕ, I_θ	0.1	D_ψ	0.1
$P_{v\phi}, P_{v\theta}$	20.0	$P_{v\psi}$	200.0
$I_{v\phi}, I_{v\theta}$	20.0	$D_{v\phi}, D_{v\theta}$	2.0

For the robotic manipulator we used right arm with the same parameters as presented in [16].

B. Human pose estimation

Our initial version of the UAV control based on human pose estimation is presented in [19]. Building on top of this work we propose a slightly different approach to enable simultaneous control of dynamically decoupled aerial manipulator. In this work, for human pose estimation we compare Simple Baselines [20] and OpenPose [12]. Compared to the previous work, instead of an RGB camera, we employed an RGBD camera (Intel Realsense D415) to extract depth measurements for complete human pose estimation in the 3D space.

Human pose estimation refers to the problem of estimating the pose of the human in relation to certain keypoints. Keypoint definition depends on the data annotations used to train the neural network. Most notable annotations for human pose estimation are MPII [21], COCO [22] and BODY25

Fig. 2: Human pose estimation for two consecutive frames k and $k + 1$ with marked arm control vectors \mathbf{p}_s^e and \mathbf{p}_s^w as well as calibration point \mathbf{c}_p and measured left wrist point \mathbf{p}_7 . Yellow point denotes origin of the shoulder coordinate frame which is used as a basis for calculating commands for the robot arm.

presented in [12] which combines COCO and MPII. In this work, we used BODY25 keypoint annotations which consist of 25 keypoints. We employed ROS wrapper of the OpenPose presented in [23]. Vector of the estimated keypoints \mathbf{h}_p contains pixel positions in the image plane of each detected keypoint. We utilize depth measurement and pixel positions to find the position vector of each detected keypoint. The human pose can be fully described with matrix \mathbf{H}_p

$$\mathbf{H}_p = [\mathbf{p}_0 \ \mathbf{p}_1 \ \dots \ \mathbf{p}_{n-1} \ \mathbf{p}_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{17 \times 3}. \quad (1)$$

Each row vector \mathbf{p}_n in \mathbf{H}_p describes position of the keypoint in the camera frame. We expand position vector \mathbf{p}_n into homogenous position vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_n$ and transform it to the world frame as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_w^n = \mathbf{T}_w^c \hat{\mathbf{p}}_n. \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{T}_w^c denotes the homogenous transformation matrix from the camera frame to the world frame. We can apply the same calculation to find the human pose relative to the AM.

IV. AERIAL MANIPULATOR CONTROL

Once all the keypoints of the human pose have been detected, the next step is to utilize this data to control the aerial manipulator. This work proposes separate control of the UAV body (i.e. UAV position control), and the separate control of the robotic manipulator attached to the UAV body (Robot manipulator control).

A. UAV position control

To control UAV we use the left wrist keypoint position vector, and initial calibration procedure. During the calibration procedure we determine the point where the left wrist is. We assume the operator is calm and positioned in such a way that further control of the AM will not exert too much physical stress. Calibration procedure refers to averaging keypoint position vector measurements for some predetermined period of time in which we collect k measurements as shown in eq. 3

$$\mathbf{c}_p = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=0}^{i=k} (\mathbf{p}_7). \quad (3)$$

Based on the measured arm movement (left wrist position) we generate a reference for the position control of the AM

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{p}_7 - \mathbf{c}_p. \quad (4)$$

We use activation factor a for reference generation as follows:

$$a = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } r_l \leq |\mathbf{r}| \leq r_u \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where r_l and $r_u \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represent lower and upper limits that are defined to prevent sending unwanted references as shown in Fig. 3. Reference generation for the position UAV control is:

$$\mathbf{p}_r = \mathbf{p}_m + a\mathbf{s} \odot \mathbf{r}. \quad (6)$$

Where \mathbf{p}_m is measured AM position in the world reference frame, a is the activation factor presented in eq. 5, element-wise multiplication is denoted with \odot , \mathbf{s} is scaling vector and \mathbf{r} is reference vector. We use a scaling vector to determine control aggressiveness. Smaller scaling vector yields smaller reference changes. Scaling parameters employed for reference generation based on human pose are presented in table III. Fig 3 depicts the proposed UAV position control interface.

TABLE III: Parameters used for reference generation

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
\mathbf{r}_l	0.05 m	\mathbf{r}_u	0.25 m
s_x	0.1	s_y	0.1
s_z	0.1		

Fig. 3: The UAV position command (eq. 6.) is derived by calculating the distance between current wrist position \mathbf{p}_7 and the average calibrated position \mathbf{c}_p .

B. Robot manipulator control

Our aerial manipulator consists of the anthropomorphic robot manipulator presented in [16]. Such a robot manipulator has 4 degrees of freedom. We want to exploit the similarities between the human arm and the anthropomorphic arm to map human arm movement to the robot arm. A straightforward method to do so is to map the angles of a human arm to the joints of the robot manipulator. Using the human pose matrix we can extract the position vector of every keypoint that is interesting to us. Keypoints that are needed to describe the motion of the human arm are the shoulder, elbow, and wrist.

As human pose estimation enables us to measure the position of key coordinate frames of the human arm, we can use the vector distance between two frames to calculate vectors from shoulder to elbow (\mathbf{p}_s^e), and elbow to wrist (\mathbf{p}_e^w). With orthogonal projection of the \mathbf{p}_s^e we can determine shoulder pitch (ϕ_s) and roll (θ_s). With orthogonal projection of the \mathbf{p}_e^w we can determine shoulder yaw (ρ_s) and elbow angle (ϕ_e). We calculate orthogonal projection of the vector \mathbf{p} on the plane M . Plane is defined by the column vectors that span matrix M . We use shoulder coordinate frame shown in Fig. 2 to obtain M .

$$proj_M \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^T \mathbf{p}. \quad (7)$$

Vector ${}^s_e \mathbf{p}_{xy}$ denotes orthogonal projection of the \mathbf{p}_e^s on the xy plane as follows:

$${}^s_e \mathbf{p}_{xy} = \mathbf{M}_{xy}(\mathbf{M}_{xy}^T \mathbf{M}_{xy})^{-1} \mathbf{M}_{xy}^T \mathbf{p}_e^s. \quad (8)$$

Matrix $\mathbf{M}_{xy} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 2}$ denotes matrix whose column space is spanned by unit vectors \hat{i} and \hat{j} . Matrix \mathbf{M}_{xz} is spanned by unit vectors \hat{i} and \hat{k} . Matrix \mathbf{M}_{yz} is spanned by unit vectors \hat{j} and \hat{k} .

Shoulder pitch angle is calculated with

$$\phi_s = \text{acos} \left(\frac{{}^e_s \mathbf{p}_{xz} \cdot \hat{k}}{\|{}^e_s \mathbf{p}_{xz}\|} \right), \quad (9)$$

Fig. 4: Shoulder coordinate frame and shoulder-elbow and elbow-wrist position vectors (\mathbf{p}_s^e , \mathbf{p}_e^w) and their orthogonal projections and determined shoulder angles (ϕ_s , θ_s , ρ_s), and elbow angle ϕ_e .

and can also be thought of as rotation about shoulder mediolateral axis. Shoulder roll angle is calculated with

$$\theta_s = \text{acos} \left(\frac{{}^e_s \mathbf{p}_{yz} \cdot \hat{k}}{\|{}^e_s \mathbf{p}_{yz}\|} \right), \quad (10)$$

and can be thought of as a rotation about shoulder anterior/posterior axis. Shoulder yaw angle is calculated with

$$\rho_s = \text{acos} \left(\frac{{}^w_e \mathbf{p}_{xy} \cdot \hat{i}}{\|{}^w_e \mathbf{p}_{xy}\|} \right), \quad (11)$$

and can be thought of as rotation about the upper arm longitudinal axis. The elbow angle is calculated with

$$\phi_e = \text{acos} \left(\frac{{}^w_e \mathbf{p}_{yz} \cdot \hat{k}}{\|{}^w_e \mathbf{p}_{yz}\|} \right), \quad (12)$$

and can be compared to the human rotation about the elbow flexion axis in humans.

Robot arm control command is then formed as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_{\text{cmd}} = [\phi_s, \theta_s, \rho_s, \phi_e] \quad (13)$$

which directly maps movement of the operators right arm to the robot manipulator.

V. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

A good simulation offers the perfect proving ground for human-machine interfaces, as it alleviates the pressure of crashing physical equipment. Previous sections describe the dynamic models used to simulate the behavior of the aerial manipulator. In this section, we briefly disseminate the simulation architecture and provide the first validation of the proposed human-machine interface.

A. System architecture

In this paragraph, we present system architecture which is composed of Hardware and Software.

1) *Hardware*: The hardware used to run experiments is PC and camera. PC configuration is Intel Core i7-10700 CPU @ 2.9 GHz x 16, an Nvidia GeForce GTX 1080Ti 11 GB GPU, and 8GB RAM. Intel Realsense D415 was used as a depth camera.

Fig. 5: Upper graph shows position control of the UAV. Dashed and dotted lines represent reference and normal lines show measured UAV position. Lower graph shows how vector r changes over time.

2) *Software:* To ensure experiment repeatability, GAZEBO 9 simulation environment on Ubuntu 18.04 was used. We used custom UAV model as explained before. For the purpose of the robot control and human pose estimation we used custom Docker files¹ and ROS melodic.

B. Validating human pose estimation

First, we compared how different pose estimations affect 3D point extraction. From Fig. 7 in Appendix it is possible to notice that shoulder and elbow have smaller position changes over time compared to the wrists. What mostly affects estimation is wrongly determined depth, which can be noticed as a sudden change (jump) in the x component. From the obtained data of the simple hand motions as follows:

- 1) increase shoulder pitch from 0° to 90° for the first 15 seconds (red area)
- 2) increase shoulder roll from 0° to 90° while reducing pitch from 90° to 0° from 15 to 30 seconds (green area)
- 3) decrease shoulder roll from 90° to 0° while increasing elbow angle from 0° to 90° from 30 to 40 seconds (blue area)

Further analyses, for easier readability, can be found in the Appendix (Section VII).

C. UAV position control

To test UAV position control, we used developed H2AMI to pass through simple maze designed in the simulation environment. Using developed position control, we successfully traversed maze. Fig. 5 shows how UAV position changes when r vector changes. We haven't imposed any constraints on the position of the UAV. Robotic arm was stationary during the UAV position control.

¹https://github.com/larics/docker_files

Fig. 6: Angles of the human arm determined by human pose estimation module for the arm control. Effects of the wrongly determined position vectors p_s^e can be seen especially on the roll angle.

D. Robot manipulator position control

For robot manipulator position control, we simply tested mapping human joint positions to the robot manipulator joint controllers based on the angles determined as described in the Section IV. Angles determined are shown in the Fig. 6. To prevent sudden changes in the angle determination, we employed averaging filter for the last five measurements.

Direct mapping performance was satisfying for basic arm movements. Easy integration and usability is limited to anthropomorphic robot arms. Wrong depth detection results in wrong pose reading, which in turns leads to wrong p_s^e and p_e^w determination. Wrong position vector determination results in wrong joint command. Sudden change of the different joints was able to disturb AM enough to crash it. In its current form, arm position control lacks robustness to be usable for the real system, however, it points out interesting research direction which could make control of the AMs intuitive and easier. It is reasonable to explore different mapping and control methods to generalize system for different robotic manipulators, as well as how to make angle determination more robust.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present H2AMI, an intuitive aerial manipulator interface based on human pose estimation. We have developed a system that allows decoupled control of UAV and RM with the operator arm movement. The movement of the left arm is used to control the UAV position, and the movement of the right arm is used to control RM. As far as we know, this is the first interface for AMs based on visual human pose estimation. Such a system has great potential, but more research and development is needed, especially in the area of robotic manipulator control. Although we can map the determined joint positions directly to the robotic manipulator, the method lacks stability and precision to be used for complex operations of all kinds. Further work will be directed toward improving the stability of the robotic arm's control, especially in the context of exploring different control strategies, and consideration of the entire aerial manipulator platform stability. Besides robot arm control, to enrich system usability, adding yaw control and perception

interface such as FPV could be beneficial. Evaluating system performance with a real robot would also be of interest.

VII. APPENDIX

For robust and reliable control, we need a stable and accurate estimate of the human pose. In this section, we present differences for keypoint pose estimation based on different human pose estimation algorithms. OpenPose has fewer sudden jumps in the estimated keypoint positions compared to the Simple Baselines. Unwanted sudden jumps of positions occur in OpenPose during arm movement. With Simple Baselines, in turn, sudden position jumps occur even when the arm is stationary, as can be clearly seen from the graph for the right and left wrist in Fig. 7. Object Keypoint Similarity (OKS) is introduced in the COCO challenge². It is computed based on the detected human scale and the distance between predicted and the ground truth keypoint. Both Simple Baselines and OpenPose use the mean Average Precision (mAP) over 10 object keypoint similarity (OKS) thresholds as a measure of the algorithm accuracy. One can compare it to the COCO test data used to report performance in both papers. Simple Baselines reports AP of 73.7, while OpenPose AP achieves AP value of 60.1. These results suggest that Simple Baselines is better, but our test showed otherwise. For our use case and camera position, OpenPose performed better, especially for the keypoints we were most interested in. Based on the observed performance, OpenPose seemed better suited for the H2AMI.

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²<https://cocodataset.org/#home>

Fig. 7: Comparison of the 3D keypoints extracted with Openpose and Simple Baselines algorithm. We compare positions of the left and right shoulder, elbow and wrist. Dashed and dotted lines represent points extracted with Simple Baselines, normal lines represent points extracted with OpenPose